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Abstract

This report is a deliverable for the project MegaRoller – Developing the PTO of the first MW-level Oscillating Wave Surge Converter. The report provides an overview of the MegaRoller project and its objectives, the work carried out within specific work packages as well as the main results and learnings achieved during the project.

MegaRoller was collaborative research and innovation project that developed and demonstrated a next-generation Power Take-Off (PTO) solution for wave energy converters. The PTO technology for a 1MW oscillating wave surge converters (OWSC) device is based on multiple hardware and software innovations. The MegaRoller project has resulted in extensive know-how in the area of PTO design and control system, while decreasing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) produced thanks to OWSC devices below €150/MWh.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

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1 INTRODUCTION

The MegaRoller project was a collaborative research and innovation project initiated in 2018 and concluded in 2021, for developing and demonstrating a next-generation Power Take-Off (PTO) solution for wave energy converters. The project was funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The PTO technology for a 1MW oscillating wave surge converters (OWSC) device is based on multiple hardware and software innovations.

The MegaRoller project has resulted in extensive know-how in the area of PTO design and control system, while decreasing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) produced thanks to OWSC devices below €150/MWh. The full-scale PTO was validated in a PTO test rig available at AW-Energy’s test facility in Finland.

The project was executed by a unique collaboration of an interdisciplinary team consisting of companies and research institutes.

Table 1-1 MegaRoller project partners

Name of organization	Acronym	Country	Type of organization
ABB Oy	ABB	Finland	Large enterprise
AW-Energy Oy	AWE	Finland	SME
K2 Management	K2M	Portugal	SME
Hydman Oy	Hydman	Finland	SME
Hydroll Oy	Hydroll	Finland	SME
Leibniz-Institut für Neurobiologie	LIN	Germany	University
SINTEF Energi AS	SINTEF	Norway	Research Institute
University of Bergen	UoB	Norway	University
VTT Oy	VTT	Finland	Research Institute
WavEC – Offshore Renewables	WavEC	Portugal	Research Institute

This report provides an overview of the work carried out in the project and the main achievements. The document is organized in the following main sections: after this introduction, the MegaRoller technology is briefly introduced. The project-specific objectives are described in chapter 2. Chapter 3 describes the main achievements of each work package. Lesson learned during the project are discussed in chapter 4.

1.1 Acronyms

AWE	AW-Energy Oy
CAPEX	Capital expenditure
CTI	Construction, testing and inspection
EIA	Environmental impact assessment
GHG	Greenhouse gas
LCA	Lifecycle assessment
LCC	Lifecycle cost
LCOE	Levelized cost of electricity
OPEX	Operational expenditure
O&M	Operation and maintenance
PTO	Power take-off system
PTT	Wave generator
PV	Photovoltaics, process of converting sunlight into electricity
SEIA	Socio-economic impact assessment
TRL5	Technology readiness level 5, technology validated in relevant environment
VRE	Variable renewable energy
WEC	Wave energy converter
WP	Work package

1.2 Technology description

The MegaRoller WEC unit is based on WaveRoller technology commercialized by AW-Energy. The device is anchored to the seabed and depending on tidal conditions it is mostly or fully submerged. A horizontal panel is affixed to the device which moves back and forth following the movement of the waves. The movement of the panel is transmitted through a drivetrain into a PTO which further converts the wave induced oscillations from mechanical energy to electricity.

Figure 1-1 MegaRoller WEC unit

The MegaRoller PTO consists of two cylinder units and a standardized power unit. As the panel moves, the PTO's hydraulic pistons pump hydraulic fluids inside a closed hydraulic circuit inside a hermetic

structure. These cylinders are composed of single action pistons, one cylinder acting when the panel moves towards the coast, and another when the movement has the opposite direction.

The MegaRoller test bench consists of wave generator (PTT), hydraulic power unit and cylinder simulating the linear movement of the WEC drivetrain as it is moved by the panel in the waves. The energy carried in the linear movement is then converted into electricity by the PTO unit. The division between the PTO and the test bench can be seen in Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-2 MegaRoller Power take-off and test bench.

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The MegaRoller project was monitored by four key activities that were identified in the beginning of the project. These are related to the development and validation of the power take-off and related systems, evaluation of technical, scientific, environmental, and socio-economic impact of the technologies as well as to dissemination, standardization, and exploitation activities.

MegaRoller project-specific objectives:

1. Develop the key components of the next generation PTO and related control systems.
2. Demonstrate and validate the performance and reliability of the next generation PTO.
3. Evaluate the technical, scientific, environmental and socio-economic impact.
4. Conduct dissemination, standardization and exploitation activities.

Key activity 1 was achieved by developing a new PTO hardware featuring modular design. The design enables the use of twin drive trains, the cylinder arrangement enables loading control, standardized central power unit and novel accumulator arrangement have been designed and implemented. In addition to the hardware design, novel PTO control systems and algorithms were designed and implemented, including wave-by-wave damping control, advanced efficiency control, energy storage control, power smoothing and prediction.

For **key activity 2**, the performance of the PTO was demonstrated and validated in various wave conditions with simulation models. The PTO system reliability and the power quality and grid compliance were validated based on the validation methodology and plans developed within the project. Finally, the results were evaluated against certification guidelines with recommendations for future activities.

To complete the objectives of **key activity 3**, an LCOE evaluation of a 10-unit, 10MW MegaRoller deployment was conducted. Furthermore, an environmental impact assessment (EIA), socio-economic impact assessment (SEIA) and life cycle assessment (LCA) were carried out.

Key activity 4 included objectives related to dissemination, standardization, and exploitation activities. Dissemination of the project results to the relevant stakeholders was ongoing throughout the duration project through various channels. Individual exploitation plans of each project partner were developed based on their contribution to the project and their business development strategy. A commercial business plan was developed for the technology.

3 WORK PACKAGES

The work in the MegaRoller project was broken down to eight work packages (WP) and further into tasks. Each work package had a dedicated lead beneficiary responsible for organizing work within their work package. The main achievements of each work package are described in the following sections.

3.1 WP1 - Interaction with the wave resource

WP1 - Interaction with the wave resource focused on developing models for environmental characterization and identification of critical loads, as well as designing and implementing the upgraded PTO test rig. The main outcomes of the work package are presented below.

3.1.1 Wave-forecasting model

A near shore *wave-forecasting model* was developed by University of Bergen to provide accurate and robust solutions for a wide range of nearshore wave processes, which include wave propagation, transformation, breaking and run-up on land. The wave-forecasting model can be used to facilitate WEC designs and to assess potential deployment sites. It will support the characterisation of a WEC deployment site, which can inform the definition of the critical design situations to consider as part of the design process (for example, by defining normal and extreme sea states), or the definition of a wave-by-wave prediction of the wavefield approaching the device, enabling a real-time adjustment of the control algorithm to optimise the PTO.

3.1.2 Load model

A distributed *load model* of the MegaRoller WEC was developed by K2Management to support the structural design of the WEC, as well as to contribute to a detailed understanding of the asynchronous loading affecting the WEC main sub-systems. In addition, a review of critical design standards, codes and device-specific design conditions to define a set of critical design load cases was carried out. The impact of novel control algorithms was also considered and the results of wave-by-wave prediction-based control methods were compared to the performance of a traditional control algorithm. Verification, pre-validation, and validation of the simulation models was conducted to ensure that the simulation models provide a reliable description of the MegaRoller PTO and the upgraded test bench behaviour in the required conditions. The pre-validation of the numerical models also used available data from the existing test bench, WaveRoller ocean testing data and wave measurement data. The numerical models were validated at the end of the project with the MegaRoller data from WP5 (see section 3.5).

3.1.3 Test bench design and implementation

The design of the new test bench was completed in WP1, including strength analysis, manufacturing drawings, and specification of the selected components. After completion of the detailed design, the components for the test bench upgrade were procured and received. The main components were supplied by the consortium partners ABB, Hydman and Hydroll. CTI (construction, testing and inspection), safety and quality assurance plans were developed to ensure quality and safety of the test bench assembly work. The software and automation system for the test bench control were implemented and the software and hardware were assembled. The assembly work included mechanical, hydraulic, and electrical assembly of the test bench, and it was executed according to the instructions created in WP4 and controlled according to the CTI plan. A third-party electrical assurance inspection was conducted to evaluate the electrical safety of the installation works.

3.2 WP2 - Design

WP2 - Design focused on the conceptual and detailed design of the MegaRoller PTO and assessing the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of the near-shore installation and developing a preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the MegaRoller wave energy converter.

3.2.1 Hydraulic design

The hydraulic layout and hydraulic components were designed in WP2, including 3D-modelling of hydraulic manifolds, hydraulic tanks and hydraulic motor-electrical generator pack. In addition, the detailed hydraulic design of the intelligent cylinders, hydraulic manifolds, hydraulic accumulators, and hydraulic motor-generator coupling was completed.

3.2.2 Electrical design

The detailed electrical design of the MegaRoller test bench, WEC, and MegaRoller array was completed in this work package, including single line diagrams, selection of components, detailed PTO electrical drawings, numerical WEC array modelling and WEC array simulations using data from the feeding network.

In connection with the electrical design, an electrical grid integration study was carried out. The results of the study showed that the electrical differences between the farm topology variations are of minor relevance. The choice of the array topology does not have significant impact on the electrical behaviour of the system. Other factors (for example, redundancy, maintenance, costs) will have more influence when the topology for a MegaRoller farm is selected. Furthermore, a market integration study on levelized value of energy was conducted. The results clearly showed that wave energy is delivering more value (per MWh) to the electricity than wind and solar energy. In the studied case, wave energy was valued on the electricity market higher than wind and solar. This number is, however, case-dependent, and it might be significantly higher if looking at a smaller power system than continental Europe (for example, Ireland). Overall, this means that wave energy does not need to reach cost-parity with wind and solar to be competitive. As it delivers higher value to the electricity market, it can also recover higher cost.

3.2.3 Mechanical design

Two different concepts were initially investigated for the final mechanical design, and the concept selection was made early in the detailed design phase based on cost and space constraints. The selected concept was analysed, and manufacturing drawings were prepared. The design provides increased reliability of the system due to the increased resilience against loads stressing of the structures. The innovation process for the final design included evaluating existing ideas and modifications of them, but the end result is unique. However, to finalise the design for production, more detailed fatigue analysis is required, and the manufacturers need to be consulted to ensure manufacturability. The location of the flexible couplings is presented in the illustration, see Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 Flexible couplings between the panel and PTO.

3.2.4 Control system design

The control system design of the power take-off (PTO) systems was completed in WP2. The main task was to design the overall control system layout. The control system consists of the automation system controlling the power take-off (PTO) units in the wave energy converter (WEC), the site controller controlling electricity production and the substation, and the site controller server collecting, storing, and sharing operational data of the site.

Figure 3-2 Overview of the MegaRoller software structure

In addition, the software innovations wave-by-wave prediction, wave-by-wave damping control, advanced energy storage control, advanced efficiency control and supervisor control were designed in this work package. The innovations are described in section 3.6.2.

3.2.5 Environmental and socio-economic acceptance

A standard method for Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) including a Socio-Economic Impact Analysis (SEIA) for wave energy projects was developed in WP2. The most relevant nearshore installations were reviewed for the assessment and an environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment standardised model was developed to work as a guideline for regulators and managers in nearshore devices, adopting an Adaptive Management (AM) approach. The model was based on an exhaustive literature survey regarding environmental effects of nearshore installations (for example, wave energy projects, pontoons and other artificial hard structures, aquaculture cages, etc.) to comprehensively address stressors, receptors and effects of this kind of structures and broaden the EIA model application. Based on this model, the environmental impact assessment tool ESIAT was developed in WP5 (see section 3.5.3).

3.2.6 Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a valuable tool that allows the assessment of the cumulative environmental impacts of a system over space and time throughout its life cycle. A preliminary LCA of the MegaRoller wave energy converter was carried out to contribute to decision making regarding the least carbon and energy intensive design choices. The LCA encompasses all life cycle stages for the wave energy converter, including the panel, foundation, PTO and mooring system, considering its deployment in Peniche, Portugal. The results of the assessment showed that the impact of manufacture is mainly due to high amounts of material used, particularly steel. Energy and carbon payback periods were both estimated to be around 28 months. An analysis of alternative scenarios was conducted showing that alternative process and design choices may increase the energy consumption and GHG emissions throughout the life cycle. While some scenarios showed a modest influence, others such as varying recycling rates and alternative material for stainless steel resulted in significant variations in the overall results. Comparison with other studies and types of power generation was made, indicating that the resulting GHG emissions and energy consumptions are generally comparable with earlier studies for wave and tidal technologies and are very low when compared with other power generating technologies. Opportunities to reduce the environmental impacts in the final design of the MegaRoller wave energy converter could potentially lie in reducing the quantity of steel by studying alternatives for its replacement.

3.3 WP3 - Implementation

WP3 - Implementation focused on implementing the design that was completed in work package 2.

The components were manufactured or procured and received in the AW-Energy's test facility in Vantaa, Finland. The hydraulic accumulators were manufactured by Hydroll, and the hydraulic manifolds by Hydman.

Figure 3-3 Hydraulic cylinders

Electrical components were procured by ABB, AW-Energy and K2Management, and mechanical components were procured by AW-Energy and K2Management.

Figure 3-4 PTO generators and LV transformer

Majority of the mechanical components were procured as assemblies, and the components included mainly passive supporting or connecting structures that were not considered hydraulic or electrical components.

Figure 3-5 Examples of cylinder assembly components

The control system software and hardware developed in WP2 were implemented. An external industrial computer was used to implement the wave prediction system. The wave prediction system receives real time data from the PTO control system, uses the received data for calculations and returns the prediction to the PTO control system. In addition, the prediction system will help implement other innovations, such as wave-by-wave damping, advanced energy storage control, and advance efficiency control into the PTO control system. It is significantly easier to adjust the PTO force control and output power control systems when the size of the incoming waves can be predicted.

Before the integration phase in WP4, a handover meeting was organized to capture the assembly requirements and to make sure that the integration team had full understanding of the assembly tasks. The meeting covered project goals, equipment and system functionality and limitations, system performance requirements, system limitations and criteria for successful operation.

3.4 WP4 - Integration

WP4 - Integration focused on the assembly work in order to integrate MegaRoller PTO from its components.

Before the assembly work, a risk assessment of the MegaRoller PTO assembly work was carried out. All risks related to the assembly work were identified, described, and analysed. Precautions were decided and listed, and a responsible person was assigned for each precaution. The probability and severity of the actuation of the risk was assessed and graded, see Table 3-1. Health and safety risks were continuously monitored during the assembly work by all workers. Changes in risks were updated to the health and safety risk assessment, and the changed risks and resulting precautions were communicated to all workers and recorded.

Table 3-1 Risk assessment grading

Probability	Severity of harm		
	1 - No injury or minor injury	2 - Lost time injury	3 - Severe injury
1 - Unlikely	1 - Very low risk	2 - Low risk	3 - Medium risk
2 - Possible	2 - Low risk	4 - Medium risk	6 - High risk
3 - Likely	3 - Medium risk	6 - High risk	9 - Very high risk

Assembly instructions and assembly order were created for the MegaRoller test bench and PTO based on their detailed designs. The instructions and assembly order take into consideration the dependencies of the sub-assemblies and spatial requirements, as well as ensure that all components fit together. Furthermore, as part of the MegaRoller PTO assembly process, a CTI (Construction, Testing, Inspection) plan was created to define the different stages of the process and the tests and inspections performed to verify the quality of the components and assembly work of the PTO. The MegaRoller PTO assembly and technical sub-assembly tests were completed in alignment with the assembly instructions, and each component was installed according to the instructions.

Figure 3-6 PTO cylinder installation and PTO installation completed

Figure 3-7 Assembled frequency converters

After the assembly, a third-party electrical assurance inspection was conducted to evaluate electrical safety and quality of installation works. The commissioning of the PTO was carried out according to the CTI plan, and the main phases of the commissioning were documented in the commissioning log. After the assembly, the PTO was ready for the full-system validation and testing carried out in WP5.

3.5 WP5 - Validation and impact evaluation

WP5 - Validation and impact evaluation focused on demonstrating, through a systematic validation process, that the models and technical solutions produced in the project meet the project objectives issued regarding PTO performance, power quality, reliability, and cost reduction.

3.5.1 Validation methodology and plans

The validation methodology and plans were developed in collaboration between VTT, AW-Energy, K2Management and WavEC. The developed methodology combined systematic analysis, simulation, and test methods, and aimed to ensure that the MegaRoller device and its PTO system meet the specified project objectives and system design requirements. The methodology covered activities for the evaluation of PTO's functional performance, output power quality and reliability performance. It also covered life cycle costs and environmental and socio-economic aspects of the MegaRoller device, its operation, and maintenance at its location. The evaluation criteria were derived and defined from the project objectives and adapted to the requirements issued by the EU for the demonstration of project results in Technology Readiness Level 5 (TRL5).

3.5.2 Validation tests

The validation tests were conducted according to the validation methodology and plans. The validation included operational tests, PTO performance measurements and PTO power quality measurements.

The purpose of *operational tests* was to verify and validate the functionality of all system components and operating modes of both the test bench and PTO system. In addition, the system was tested for safe operation. The system operation itself was also tested to validate correct operation in each operating mode of the system and during the transitions between the operating modes. The validation included PTO's functional performance and output power quality. The results showed that all operation modes functioned as expected and transitions between the modes were fluent. Furthermore, the system response to alarms was validated successfully.

The purpose of *PTO performance tests* was to determine whether the MegaRoller PTO can reach and maintain its nominal power output. Power conversion efficiency of the PTO was assessed to reach understanding on the optimal operating parameters for the PTO and to evaluate the efficiency. In addition, the PTO control system was tested in emulations that resemble the real-world operation where the power input from the waves varies by time. The validation results showed that the PTO control system operated as expected with all four wave input emulations proving the correct performance of the control system. This was verified as the system reached a stable variance in operating pressure and power output. The amplitude of variance is dependent on the accumulator capacity, which can be increased to reach more stable operation.

The purpose of *power quality* measurements was to validate the power quality from the MegaRoller PTO by emulating actual sea states based on sea states measured from the coastline of Peniche, Portugal. The results showed that the MegaRoller PTO is able to operate according to power quality standards.

However, some hardware and software improvements need to be done to the testing setup for getting better results.

3.5.3 Environmental impact assessment and socio-economic impact assessment

The environmental and socio-economic impact assessment tool ESIAT was developed based on the findings in WP2 and from further literature review. The application of the ESIAT to the MegaRoller installation rendered a complex and extensive document that includes the potential environmental and socioeconomic impacts expected from the MegaRoller installation and their mitigation measures. The expected potential impacts include e.g. disruption of the seabed morphology, deterioration of sediment quality, and disruption of the benthic communities. While many of the potential impacts are negative, some positive impacts are also expected, such as artificial reef effect enhancing local biodiversity, new opportunities for businesses and employment). At present, the negative impacts with greater significance are expected during the preparation and construction phases. The preparation and construction phases the project development may be negatively perceived by its potential impacts on the environment and on local commercial activities (e.g., fishing). During the operation phase, the installations require an extensive section of the maritime space which may pose restrictions for sea users, namely the local communities and businesses that rely on fishing as their sole or primary income. Hence, in common to other MRE projects, social acceptance will be crucial to develop MegaRoller.

Furthermore, the LCA study carried out under WP2 was adjusted to the final design version of the MegaRoller device to assess its environmental impacts. The LCA was intended to choose the least carbon intensive design option for the WEC and opting for the most efficient processes throughout the device's life cycle. The results indicated that the impact of manufacture is mainly due to high amounts of material used, particularly steel. Energy and carbon payback periods were both estimated to be around 28 months. The study confirms the effectiveness of LCA as a tool for assessing environmental impacts of marine renewable energy sources and comparing results with alternative energy sources and informing decisions for concept and product development.

3.5.4 Life cycle cost assessment

Based on the cost structure and the LCC methodology presented in section 3.5.1, a tailored MegaRoller LCC tool was developed. The tool can be used to assess all the costs through the entire lifetime of the MegaRoller device from design to the retirement phase and for making cost scenarios for the various MegaRoller designs, O&M strategies, and failure situations. The tool was also used for conducting the LCC case study, a wave energy project where the MegaRoller device is located at the coast of Portugal, in Peniche. The total life cycle, discounted life cycle cost as well as annual cost and discounted cumulative cost are calculated as result indicators of the LCC. Early implementation of the LCC influences the design changes and provides explanations of the relationships between cost and design parameters. Long-term life cycle cost reduction will be achieved by innovating but also by increased competition and deployment and by sharing synergies with other offshore sectors. The LCC contributes to cost reduction by identifying high-cost contributors. Thus, it supports the designers to make transparent and systematic decisions as it creates a common understanding of the cost impacts of the various design options before the actual decision takes place.

3.6 WP6 - Dissemination, standardization, and exploitation

WP6 - Dissemination, standardization, and exploitation focused on the dissemination of project results and the development of an ecosystem of partners along the manufacturing value chain, in order to guarantee a sustainable impact to the project, once it is completed.

3.6.1 Communication and dissemination activities

The goal of the communication and dissemination activities of the results activities was to promote the action and inform relevant audiences about the expected outcome and exploitation opportunities. Project partners were involved in several events, workshops, conferences and stakeholder activities. Several conference talks as well as papers in conferences and events were given. A joint side event was promoted and arranged in Dublin at the Ocean Energy Europe OEE 2019 conference with five presentations from four partners. Blogs of the activity and scientific aspects were written for the project website www.megaroller.eu, and there are also several open articles for the general public.

Video interviews posted with the WP leaders and the CEO of AW-Energy explaining the project objectives and work packages were produced and made public on the project website. To replace cancelled workshops due to the Covid-19 restrictions, a feature film and a series of scientific presentations were filmed and distributed on the project website. In the website visitors can also find open news articles, pictures, fact sheets, blogs, deliverables, documents and other information about MegaRoller.

In addition, a Sharepoint site hosted by SINTEF was used for internal document sharing and communications between the consortium members.

3.6.2 Innovation management

The MegaRoller project identified several innovation areas prior to the project. To manage the innovations and IPR resulted from the project, an innovation strategy was developed. The majority of the innovations were made in the design phase of the project. The protection measures for the generated intellectual property are ongoing even after the project has ended. The innovations made during the project included both hardware and software innovations, and they were listed in the IPR registry produced during the project. The MegaRoller innovations are illustrated in Figure 3-8, and described briefly below.

Figure 3-8 MegaRoller innovations.

The *modular MegaRoller PTO design* has a modular structure in the arrangement the main units: there are two PTOs on both sides of the panel and the Central Power Unit. Also, the internal component arrangement of the PTO is highly modular. The greatest advantage of modularity inside the PTO is that the modules can be exchanged and adjusted for MegaRoller WEC according to varying wave resource, ambient conditions (e.g. sea water temperature) and customer requirements. Modularity is an advantage also regarding the maintenance.

The MegaRoller *twin drive train* consists of two drive trains: one on each side of the panel, inside the PTO housing. The twin drive train arrangement makes it possible to utilize two PTOs with a single panel and increase the rated power to 1MW.

Three *intelligent cylinder* concepts were designed to remove pressure spikes from the MegaRoller hydraulic cylinder circuit. Because of the lengthy investigation process with the cylinders the concepts will be investigated further in the future. The optimal solution is most probably a combination of different concepts.

The purpose of the *electric central unit* is to connect the two PTO units of the MegaRoller and feed the power to the grid. All communication routes between the PTO units and between the substation and the PTOs are also routed via the central unit. The central unit will have a cylinder-shaped hull with detachable round end flanges in both ends. In most cases, a round cylindrical shape in underwater structure provides the best weight-cost-volume ratio since it is easy to manufacture and naturally has good endurance against external pressure variations.

A machine-learning algorithm to produce *wave-by-wave predictions* is integrated in the MegaRoller PTO control systems software to give an input to damping algorithm. The algorithm predictions are used in PTO damping control for optimized power capture. This algorithm is based on Echo State Networks (ESN), a relatively new scheme for training highly nonlinear recurrent neural networks to perform time series prediction. The ESN has been modified by adapting methods from computational neuroscience building the ESN to mimic the auditory cortex of the brain. New ways of training the ESN were also developed.

Figure 3-9 Prediction algorithm mimicking the auditory cortex of the brain

By applying *wave-by-wave damping* it is possible to capture significantly more energy from the moving panel. The input for the damping algorithm is the wave estimate given by the wave prediction algorithm.

An *efficient energy storage control* based on modelling the fill level of the hydraulic accumulators has been developed. Based on the information of the incoming waves (the wave prediction) and the fill level of accumulators, usage of the energy storage can be optimized. Depending on the predicted size of waves coming in, the output power of the device can be adjusted to be able to, on the other hand store all the energy coming, but also to keep the output power adequately stable.

Advanced efficiency control is a combination of controlling multiple PTO subsystems in optimized way. The subsystems include cylinder packs, accumulators, motor-generator packs, and cooling.

The *supervisor controller* controls site output power and grid support functionality, e.g. frequency regulation. The controller is a PLC connected via fast data transfer channel to individual devices, enabling real-time control. The parametrization of the supervisor controller is done in SCADA, and the controller operates autonomously based on those parameters.

3.6.3 Exploitation planning

An exploitation strategy for the management of project results was developed as part of the work package. The individual exploitation plans of each project partner were based on their contributions to the project and their own business development strategy. The exploitable results of the MegaRoller project, the target customers for the developed solution and the exploitation model were identified by each project partner. The competitive landscape of the project was monitored during the project, focusing on the market prospects of the MegaRoller WEC as a technology for utility-scale power production, including development and state of the potential renewable electricity and hydrogen markets for the MegaRoller technology, progression of other actors and technologies within the field of wave energy, and potential applicability of the MegaRoller technology in other WEC types. Furthermore, it has been identified that both public funds and private investors provide funding opportunities for activities after the MegaRoller project.

3.6.4 Industrial business cases

The project produced a commercial business plan including potential commercial applications of the developed technology, review of the existing markets and forecast of future demand for the applications. In addition, two business cases were developed for the solution in European markets: *Case A* for the production of electricity in the Irish energy markets, and *Case B* for the production of green hydrogen in Portugal.

In *Case A*, the power production in the coast near Killard, Ireland, was simulated using wave timeseries data, technical characteristics of the MegaRoller PTO, and a corresponding panel design. The results of the simulation showed that the average annual power generation for an 8 MW wave farm would generate an income ranging between €1,920,000 and €2,688,000 using the local electricity pricing.

The site for the business *Case B* is near Peniche, Portugal, where the power generation of the MegaRoller WECs was estimated based on wave timeseries data. The simulation resulted in annual hydrogen production of 350 metric tons. Additionally, 1,174 MWh of electricity was dispatched to the grid per year. Total annual income from sales of hydrogen and electricity would range between €1.8 million and €3.6 million. The variance in the annual income is relatively large due to the high uncertainties of future electricity and green hydrogen retail prices. The annual spread of hydrogen and power production with the considered capacities is presented in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10 Monthly hydrogen and power production

Throughout the MegaRoller project, further opportunities for the technology were also identified in the production of freshwater through desalination of seawater, in providing frequency support services for grid operators, and in applications in other wave energy conversion technologies. The MegaRoller project focused on the core technical component of the MegaRoller WEC, which is the power take-off unit. Further efforts are required to develop the remaining system and realize the value generated through the project as well as the broader impacts and potential of the MegaRoller technology.

3.6.5 Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE)

The final modelled levelized cost of electricity for the MegaRoller technology was developed in WP6 including formulas to calculate the LCOE. The achieved range of levelized costs of energy for the MegaRoller technology is 148-100 €/MWh. Further costs reductions are expected to be realized through increased deployments of the technology and to follow a costs reduction trajectory similar to other variable renewable energy technologies. Following 50 MW of cumulative deployment LCOE is forecast to reach 116-60 €/MWh and in the most conservative assessment decline below 100 EUR/MWh after 130 MW deployed capacity.

Figure 3-11 Project contributions to decrease LCOE

The ability of the MegaRoller technology to supplement other renewable energy technologies in the electricity mix and to extract a higher value per produced kilowatt hour was also modelled. As wave power is not correlated with the day-night-cycle of solar radiation nor the local wind climate determining wind power production, wave energy can support a power grid with increased solar and wind production capacity and proportionately deployed claim a higher price per kWh produced. The development of the PTO technology for OWSC technologies carried out through the MegaRoller project and the achieved results are highly encouraging for further decrease of costs and uptake of wave energy.

3.6.6 Standardization activities

WP6 contributed on the development of standards related to marine energy and offshore installations of power systems. The existing standards and guidelines from the industry were reviewed by project partners, and input was provided on standard and guideline requirements. A standard gap analysis was carried out on the certification related to technology. The need for further certification and accreditation of sub-systems, components or methods was continuously assessed throughout the project, and gaps in the standards were identified for future development of standards.

3.6.7 Data management activities

Research data created in the project was deposited in a repository that facilitates linking publications and underlying data through persistent identifiers and data citations. During the 44 months of the active project, a Sharepoint site was used as the working and collaboration area for the project and for uploading all data sets with relevant metadata. The [Zenodo](#) repository was used to comply to H2020 Open Access Mandate aiming to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protecting of sensitive data due to commercial or security reasons. In the MegaRoller project, no public research data was available for upload due to confidentiality reasons.

3.7 WP7 - Scientific coordination

WP7 - Scientific coordination included the activities of the project manager, AW-Energy, in managing the consortium. The main goal of the project management was the efficient technical implementation of the action. The project management plan, a document produced in the beginning of the project, was used as the main planning document throughout the project. In addition, a project quality handbook was developed to outline the implemented quality assurance process, overviewing how the project is conducted, assessed, monitored, accounted for and safeguarded during and after its key tasks.

The scientific coordinator was responsible for monitoring the progress of the work packages, coordinating the technical content for the reporting, reviewing the quality of the deliverables produced during the project, and uploading them to the project portal. In addition, the scientific coordinator organized regular meetings with the executive board, advisory board as well as with the consortium members, monitored significant technical project risks, and informed and negotiated changes and challenges of the project with the EC Project Manager.

3.8 WP8 - Coordination

WP8 - Coordination covered the activities of the project coordinator, Hydroll, in coordinating the MegaRoller project in close cooperation with the scientific coordinator. The coordinator was responsible for monitoring the implementation of the actions and acting as the intermediary for communication between the beneficiaries and the European Commission. Furthermore, the coordinator verified the completeness and correctness of the deliverables before submitting them to the EC.

The coordinator received the EC financial contribution on behalf of the consortium and distributed the contribution to each partner. In addition, project reviews and progress reporting were organized by the coordinator in cooperation with the scientific coordinator.

4 EXPERIENCES AND LESSONS LEARNED

The following sections describe the experiences and knowledge gained from the process of conducting the MegaRoller project. The project faced severe unexpected setbacks, such as the termination of the test facility's rental agreement and the Covid-19 outbreak. In addition, there were issues that were not considered in the planning phase of the project and caused additional workload and costs. Despite the difficulties, the project partners persistently sought solutions to keep the project on track and were able to achieve the main objectives of the project.

4.1 Unforeseen challenges

The project faced a major challenge during its first months, when the rental agreement of AW-Energy's test facility was unexpectedly terminated in October 2018. This resulted in some adjustments to the project schedule. Originally, the purpose was to enhance the existing AW-Energy test facility in Finland to be suitable for the MegaRoller project. AW-Energy was forced to find a new facility and secure it for the duration of the project. Additional investment was also needed for the disassembly and rebuilding the new facility.

However, the most significant challenge in the project was the COVID-19 outbreak in February 2020, which caused further delays in the project and had similar negative effects in all partner countries. Consequently, the consortium was forced to apply for a project extension of 8 months to be able to achieve its objectives. Despite all the difficulties, the project partners persistently sought solutions to keep the project on track. For example, tools, procedures, and instructions were set up to enable remote work, new resources were hired, face-to-face meetings were replaced by remote meetings, and the final event was replaced by a video series for scientific audiences and a feature film for a broader audience.

Presenting the project results to stakeholders was difficult due to the Covid-19 restrictions, as the project result was a physical device. It was impossible to have a proper understanding of the MegaRoller PTO and test bench remotely, therefore visits to the test facility would have been valuable in communicating the project progress.

Not all impacts of the pandemic were negative. Virtual meetings proved to be successful: a larger group of interested participants was able to join the meetings as traveling was not required, and therefore information was disseminated to a wider audience.

4.2 Project planning

Prior to the start of the project, a Grant Agreement (GA) was signed by all partners. The GA sets out the rights and obligations and the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to the partners for implementing the MegaRoller project. By signing the GA, the partners accepted the grant and agreed to implement it under their own responsibility and in accordance with the agreement, with all the obligations and conditions it set out. The content for the Grant Agreement, Annex 1 "Description of the action" was provided by the consortium. This describes the objectives, tasks, and deliverables of the project. During the project it became evident that the content of Annex 1 should have been more carefully considered. For example, it would have been better to exclude too specific technical details if it was not certain that these can be implemented. As the project was granted based on the terms laid out in the GA, the GA needed to be revised if it was not possible to implement the actions.

Finding resources with required technical expertise and experience was challenging, especially in the field of mechanical engineering, as the project was so unique. A lot of time and effort was put into finding the right people for the project. In addition, there was some employee turnover in the project organizations, and it was difficult to find new resources to replace them. These changes had a negative impact on the partner organizations' commitment to the project.

Partner organizations produced several report deliverables during the project. Their key purpose was to facilitate internal and external communication. Report deliverables aimed at presenting and transferring the know-how, results and knowledge generated by and during the project. The EC will determine that the project is complete and has met the expected requirements by reference to the deliverables defined in the project program. It was therefore essential that the quality of the deliverables was monitored and assessed internally throughout the project. During the course of the project, it was noticed that the review process of the report deliverables was more time consuming than had been anticipated in the schedule planning. Some of the reports were extensive and contained a lot of detailed information, and their review was laborious. Especially if there were several peer review rounds, it sometimes took several weeks to have the acceptance for the deliverable. In addition, sometimes the EC requested amendments to the report which led to further internal review rounds of the revised report. Consequently, the lengthy review process sometimes caused delays in the submissions.

The importance of procurement planning was not emphasized enough in the beginning of the project. For example, procurement was handled by relatively small organizations that did not have a lot of experience, and thus there were some surprises during the project. The procurement was budgeted before the project started, but the prices of materials had increased since then quite significantly, mostly due to the Covid-19 outbreak. For the same reason, also the availability of materials was limited. There should have been some buffer in the budget for such changes, as well as for possible value added tax (VAT) that was added to the price of purchased items in some cases.

4.3 Technical issues

After the Covid-19 outbreak, the price level of materials and components was significantly higher than originally budgeted, and their availability was limited. This forced AW-Energy to make technical adjustments to the design to be able to stay on budget. Consequently, the design changes affected the schedule, and because of the design changes, the Grant Agreement needed to be updated accordingly.

There were some quality issues in the basic steel structures, which caused additional delays in the assembly phase. For example, poor quality was seen in threaded holes and some dimensions were incorrect. Furthermore, some unexpected oil leaks were discovered in the test bench that were later solved but caused additional delays in the commissioning phase.

In addition, there were challenges in reporting the detailed design on schedule. Similar challenge was faced with completing the PTO validation testing. The design process and validation testing are iterative processes that were continuously improved. Thus, the design and validation test reports presented the current, but not the final, status of the work.